

CERTIFICATE OF APPRECIATION

THIS CERTIFIES THAT
TAFAKKUR MANZILI
JURNALIDA FAOL ISHTIROK ETGANI UCHUN

Bekturdiyeva Guli Sodiqjon qizi

DESCRIPTION OF HUMAN EMOTIONS IN GUY DE MAUPASSANT'S WORKS

NOMLI MAQOLASI BILAN ISHTIROK ETGANI UCHUN TAQDIRLANADI

2023/YANVAR

